

EXERCISES MENTIONED IN THE ANTIPATTERNS CATALOGS

Exercise 1.1 - Develop a code that reads an integer entered by the user and prints the value typed.

Exercise 1.2 - Develop a code that receives an integer (int), typed by the user, and prints the square of that number.

Exercise 2.1 - Develop a code that reads two integers typed by the user and prints the largest of the two numbers.

Exercise 2.2 - Develop a code that reads two integers as inputs (say in variables a and b) and prints 1 if "a < b" and 0 otherwise.

Exercise 3.1 - Develop a code in C or Python that checks whether 3 numbers can represent the angles of a triangle or not. Your algorithm should prompt the user to enter the 3 natural numbers (representing angles in degrees) and print: "Sim" (Yes) and the 3 numbers in the sequence entered if they add up to 180, and "NAO" (NO) and the sum of the 3 numbers otherwise.

Exercise 3.2 - Develop a code that reads three natural numbers as inputs and checks to see if those numbers are Pythagorean. Three numbers are Pythagorean if the square of the largest of them (hypotenuse) is equal to the sum of the square of the other two. Your program should print: if Pythagorean, the value "1" and the value of the hypotenuse squared; if not Pythagorean, only the value "0".

The numbers are called Pythagorean because they correspond to side lengths of a right triangle, i.e., $h^2 = a^2 + b^2$.

Exercise 3.3 - Develop a C/Python program that reads a natural (say in the "total" variable) and computes the largest sum of consecutive naturals, starting at 1, that is less than or equal to the value entered (\leq total).

Exercise 4.1 - Develop a program with functions named "soma" (sum) and "media" (average), both with 2 formal parameters of type "int", which respectively return the sum of the parameters and their average. Functions must have 2 integer parameters, such as "soma(a, b)" and "media(a, b)". Your main program should receive from the user 2 integers, invoke with them first the sum function and print their sum, then invoke media and print their arithmetic mean (invoking the functions).

Exercise 4.2 - Make a program in C / Python necessarily implementing a function named "fat," with one parameter "n," which, given an integer "n," returns the factorial of "n" if "n \geq 0,"

otherwise return "-1." Make a "main" program that prompts the user to type any integer and using the function "fat" print the factorial of the natural typed.

Remember, the factorial function fat (n) is defined only for naturals (with zero), as follows: fat (0) = 1 and fat (n) = n * fat (n-1), n > 0. Thus, for example, the factorial of 4 is computed as follows: fat (4) = 4! = 4.3.2.1 = 24.

Thus, you must agree what to do if you enter a negative integer, in which case your program should print -1 (e.g., if the input is: n = -10 => output -1; n = -21 => output -1).

Exercise 4.7 - Develop a code that receives a positive natural number n (n >= 1) and then a list of "n" non-null integer values, each followed by a 0 (ending the subsequence), calculating the sum of odd numbers of each subsequence and print them (as soon as you read each 0).

Examples: For the subsequences below, all with n = 3

Ex. 1. Inputs (including n): 3 0 0 0 => outputs: 0

Ex. 2. Inputs (including n): 3 2 0 2 0 2 0 => outputs: 0

Ex. 3. Inputs (including n): 3 1 0 3 0 5 0 => outputs: 1 3 5)

Exercise 7.1 - Construct an algorithm that receives a positive natural n (n > 0) and prints the sum of the first n terms of the harmonic series defined below.

$$H = 1/1 + 1/2 + 1/3 + 1/4 + \dots + 1/k + \dots$$

Exercise 7.2 - Build an algorithm that takes a positive natural number and real value (n and x), calculates and prints the value of x n. (power from x to n). Use only the sum and product operators.

Exercise 7.4 - Build a program that receives an integer n and then n characters as input by printing the ASCII (American Standard Code for Information Interchange) codes for each character.

Exercise 8.1 - 1. Implement a function called "determineSeOrdenado" that takes as parameters an integer "n" and array of integers called "vet". The function should return "1" if the elements in vet[] are in ascending order and "0" otherwise (that is, if vet[0] < vet[1] < ... < vet[n-1], returns 1 and in any other setting returns 0).

2. Make a "main" program in which the user types a number "n>0", followed by "n" integer values that are stored in the array (which can have up to 40 elements). Using the value returned by the function of item 1, your program should print "1" if the array is in ascending order and "0" otherwise.

Exercise 13.1 - Make a program in which the user enters positive integers "m" and "n" ($m > 0$, $n > 0$), followed by $m \times n$ real values (float), which should be stored in a matrix of order $m \times n$. Then your program should print each line, followed by the "=" sign and the sum of the line, starting at line 0, then line 1, and so on. Thus, you must first print the value of $M[0][0]$, followed by $M[0][1]$ and so on to the last of the line ($M[0][n-1]$) and then the equal sign and the sum of the number from line zero. Then follow lines 2, 3 to $m-1$.